

Studies on Some Indophenazines

S. K. GUHA, K. D. BANERJI[†] and K. K. SEN

Chemistry Department, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-7

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Fiftysix variously substituted indophenazines have been prepared and dyeing shades of several of them have been developed on wool.

SOME 6H-indolo (2,3-b) quinoxalines, commonly called indophenazines, have earlier been prepared and studied from different viewpoints. Thus while Buu-Hoi *et al* have investigated their inhibitory effect on tuberculosis bacillies and haemolytic streptococcus and also their general toxicity and carcinogenic effect¹⁻⁵, Friedman⁶ has obtained other indophenazines which are useful as optical bleaches. Recently⁷, some indophenazines have been found to be good antispasmodics.

The known indophenazines⁸⁻¹¹ vary in colour from sulphur yellow to red, although two are reported to

be black. They mostly contain substituents in the indole system and only a few in the benzene moiety as well. It was therefore considered interesting to prepare indophenazines carrying substituents in positions 1 to 4 and in general, also in the indole moiety. These compounds were expected to be highly coloured and act as dyes to wool and may have biological activities.

The indophenazines described herein, have been prepared by the condensation of isatin or its derivatives with 3-chloro-, 3-bromo-, 3-iodo-¹², 4-methoxy-, 4,5-dimethyl, 4,5-dichloro and 4,6-dibromo-*o*-phenylenediamines. The products are obtained in good yield and in general, are soluble in nitrobenzene and pyridine, moderately soluble in acetic acid and almost insoluble in ethanol, acetone and ether.

In some cases, the condensation may obviously lead to the production of structural isomers. Although exact structure assignment was not undertaken, it was observed that only one of the isomers is almost invariably predominantly produced and

TABLE. MICROANALYTICAL AND OTHER DATA OF THE INDOPHENAZINES PREPARED

Sl. No.	Reactants*	Appearance; (Solvent of crystallisation)	M.P. °C	Yield (%)	(a) Colour with conc. H ₂ SO ₄ ; (b) Shade on wool	Mol. formula	Analysis N%	
							Found	Reqd.
<i>Section I</i>								
1.	I+3-Chloro-P	Deep yellow needles; (Acetic acid)	319-20	(58)	(a) Deep brown	C ₁₄ H ₈ ClN ₃	16.1	16.6
2.	5-Chloro-I+3-chloro-P	Orange flakes; (Ethylacetate)	316-18	(59)	(a) Brown (b) Bright yellow	C ₁₄ H ₇ Cl ₂ N ₃	14.4	14.6
3.	5-Bromo-I+3-chloro-P	Bright orange needles; (Nitrobenzene)	314-16	(51)	(a) Deep brown (b) Bright yellow	C ₁₄ H ₇ BrClN ₃	12.0	12.6
4.	5-Iodo-I+3-chloro-P	Orange yellow granules; (Nitrobenzene)	318-20	(95)	(a) Yellow with greenish tinge (b) Dull yellow	C ₁₄ H ₇ ClN ₃	10.9	11.1
5.	5-Nitro-I+3-chloro-P	Dull deep yellow needles; (Nitrobenzene)	352-54(d)	(94)	(a) Brownish orange	C ₁₄ H ₇ ClN ₄ O ₂	18.6	18.8
6.	5,7-Dibromo-I+3-chloro-P	Light orange yellow needles; (Acetic acid + Ethylacetate)	302-304	(92)	(a) Light brown	C ₁₄ H ₆ Br ₂ ClN ₃	9.8	10.2

[†] To whom all correspondence be addressed.

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Sl. No.	Reactants*	Appearance; (Solvent of crystallisation)	M.P. °C	Yield (%)	(a) Colour with conc. H ₂ SO ₄ ; (b) Shade on wool	Mol. formula	Analysis N%	
							Found	Reqd.
7.	5-Bromo-7-nitro-I+3-chloro-P	Reddish orange granules; (Pyridine)	330-32	(81)	(a) Red (b) Intense orange	C ₁₄ H ₆ BrClN ₄ O ₂	14.7	14.8
8.	5,7-Dinitro-I+3-chloro-P	Deep yellow granules (Nitrobenzene)	320-25(d)	(97)	(a) Bright orange red	C ₁₄ H ₆ ClN ₅ O ₄	20.0	20.4
<i>Section II</i>								
9.	I+3-Bromo-P	Lemon yellow woolly needles; (Chloroform)	294-95	(69)	(a) Deep reddish brown (b) Lemon yellow	C ₁₄ H ₈ BrN ₃	14.3	14.1
10.	5-Chloro-I+3-bromo-P	Dull orange woolly needles; (Ethanol+Ethylacetate)	316-18	(59)	(a) Deep brown (b) Dull light yellow	C ₁₄ H ₇ BrClN ₃	12.5	12.6
11.	5-Bromo-I+3-bromo-P	Shining orange needles; (Nitrobenzene)	305-306	(59)	(a) Brown (b) Yellow with brownish tinge	C ₁₄ H ₇ Br ₂ N ₃	11.0	11.1
12.	5-Iodo-I+3-bromo-P	Light brown needles; (Nitrobenzene)	295-96(d)	(52)	(a) Brownish yellow (b) Brownish yellow	C ₁₄ H ₇ BrIN ₃	9.3	9.9
13.	5-Nitro-I+3-bromo-P	Deep yellow woolly needles; (Nitrobenzene)	358	(79)	(a) Deep orange (b) Dirty yellow	C ₁₄ H ₇ BrN ₄ O ₂	16.1	16.3
14.	5,7-Dibromo-I+3-bromo-P	Orange red woolly needles; (Nitrobenzene)	315-17	(77)	(a) Light orange (b) Orange yellow	C ₁₄ H ₆ Br ₂ N ₃	9.0	9.2
15.	5-Bromo-7-nitro-I+3-bromo-P	Shining bright orange-red needles; (Nitrobenzene)	311-14	(78)	(a) Deep brown (b) Orange	C ₁₄ H ₆ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₂	13.0	13.2
16.	5,7-Dinitro-I+3-bromo-P	Intense lemon yellow; (Nitrobenzene)	317-20	(54)	(a) Orange (b) Intense lemon yellow	C ₁₄ H ₆ BrN ₅ O ₄	17.7	18.0
<i>Section III</i>								
17.	I+3-iodo-P	Yellow woolly needles; (Nitrobenzene)	288-90	(67)	(a) Reddish brown	C ₁₄ H ₆ IN ₃	12.3	12.2
18.	5-Chloro-I+3-iodo-P	Deep orange prisms; (Acetic acid)	356-57	(60)	(a) Brown (b) Yellow with orange tinge	C ₁₄ H ₇ ClIN ₃	10.9	11.1
19.	5-Bromo-I+3-iodo-P	Brownish yellow flakes; (Nitrobenzene)	367-68	(71)	(a) Brown	C ₁₄ H ₇ BrIN ₃	9.7	9.9
20.	5-Iodo-I+3-iodo-P	Brownish yellow flakes; (Nitrobenzene)	373-75	(64)	(a) Deep brown	C ₁₄ H ₇ I ₂ N ₃	8.6	8.9
21.	5-Nitro-I+3-iodo-P	Deep yellow granules; (Nitrobenzene)	330-32	(96)	(a) Deep yellowish brown	C ₁₄ H ₇ IN ₄ O ₂	14.3	14.4
22.	5,7-Dibromo-I+3-iodo-P	Bright orange woolly needles; (Nitrobenzene)	328-30	(80)	(a) Yellow brown (b) Brownish yellow	C ₁₄ H ₆ Br ₂ IN ₃	7.9	8.3
23.	5-Bromo-7-nitro-I+3-iodo-P	Orange-red flakes; (Nitrobenzene)	322	(87)	(a) Deep yellowish brown (b) Deep brown	C ₁₄ H ₆ BrIN ₄ O ₂	11.8	12.0
24.	5,7-Dinitro-I+3-iodo-P	Deep yellow granules; (Nitrobenzene)	377(d)	(90)	(a) Reddish brown (b) Yellow	C ₁₄ H ₆ IN ₅ O ₄	16.0	16.1
<i>Section IV</i>								
25.	I+4-methoxy-P	Lemon yellow fluorescent needles; (Acetic acid)	262	(24)	(a) Deep brownish red	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O	16.4	16.9
26.	5-Chloro-I+4-methoxy-P	Lemon yellow flakes; (Pyridine)	346-48	(39)	(a) Ruby red	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O	14.4	14.8

* I = Isatin;

P = orthophenylenediamine.

TABLE—Contd.

Sl. No.	Reactants*	Appearance; (Solvent of crystallisation)	M.P. °C	Yield (%)	(a) Colour with conc. H ₂ SO ₄ ; (b) Shade on wool	Mol. formula	Analysis N%	
							Found	Reqd.
27.	5-Bromo-I+ 4-methoxy-P	Light lemon yellow granules; (Pyridine)	348-50	(19)	(a) Brownish red	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ BrN ₃ O	12.5	12.8
28.	5-Iodo-I+ 4-methoxy-P	Lemon yellow with greenish tinge granules; (Pyridine)	325-27	(38)	(a) Brownish red	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ IN ₃ O	11.1	11.4
29.	5-Nitro-I+ 4-methoxy-P	Deep yellow woolly needles; (Pyridine)	329-33(d)	(89)	(a) Ruby red (b) Deep yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₃	18.8	19.0
30.	5,7-Dibromo-I+ 4-methoxy-P	Deep yellow granules; (Pyridine)	298-99	(94)	(a) Ruby red (b) Dirty yellow	C ₁₅ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₃ O	10.0	10.3
31.	5-Bromo-7-nitro- I+4-methoxy-P	(i) Deep yellow cryst; (Chloroform) (ii) Orange cryst; (Nitrobenzene+ Pyridine)	283-84 331-32	(97)*	(ia) Pink red (iia) Orange red (iib) Dirty brown	C ₁₅ H ₉ BrN ₄ O ₃	14.9	15.0
32.	5,7-Dinitro-I+ 4-methoxy-P	Light yellow woolly needles; (Chloroform)	341(d)	(88)	(a) Ruby red (b) Dirty light yellow	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₅ O ₅	20.3	20.6
<i>Section V</i>								
33.	I+4,5-Dimethyl- P	Light lemon yellow flakes; (Acetic acid)	352-53	(69)	(a) Deep orange	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃	17.0	17.0
34.	5-Chloro-I+ 4,5-dimethyl-P	Lemon yellow woolly needles; (Acetic acid)	370-71	(50)	(a) Deep brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClN ₃	14.8	14.9
35.	5-Bromo-I+ 4,5-dimethyl-P	Brownish yellow shining flakes; (Nitrobenzene)	360-61	(46)	(a) Deep orange (b) Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ BrN ₃	12.6	12.9
36.	5-Iodo-I+ 4,5-dimethyl-P	Yellow brown woolly needles; (Nitrobenzene)	320-24	(78)	(a) Deep brown (b) Dirty yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ IN ₃	11.5	11.3
37.	5-Nitro-I+ 4,5-dimethyl-P	Light brown woolly needles; (Nitrobenzene+ Pyridine)	365(d)	(82)	(a) Deep reddish orange	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂	18.8	19.2
38.	5,7-Dibromo-I+ 4,5-dimethyl-P	Yellow flakes; (Nitrobenzene)	317	(56)	(a) Deep orange	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Br ₂ N ₃	9.9	10.4
39.	5-Bromo-7-nitro- I+4,5-dimethyl-P	Yellow orange woolly needles; (Nitrobenzene)	355(d)	(88)	(a) Deep orange	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrN ₄ O ₂	14.8	15.1
40.	5,7-Dinitro-I+ 4,5-dimethyl-P	Orange flakes; (Nitrobenzene)	325-26	(42)	(a) Deep orange (b) Light yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₄	20.9	20.8
<i>Section VI</i>								
41.	I+4,5-dichloro-P	Lemon yellow flakes; (Pyridine)	374-75	(72)	(a) Deep reddish brown	C ₁₄ H ₇ Cl ₂ N ₃	15.3	14.6
42.	5-Chloro-I+ 4,5-dichloro-P	Dark red granules; (Ethyl acetate)	370-72	(72)	(a) Deep reddish brown	C ₁₄ H ₆ Cl ₃ N ₃	12.9	13.0
43.	5-Bromo-I+ 4,5-dichloro-P	Dull orange shining prisms; (Pyridine)	380-84	(82)	(a) Deep brown (b) Reddish orange	C ₁₄ H ₆ BrCl ₂ N ₃	11.1	11.5
44.	5-Iodo-I+ 4,5-dichloro-P	Dark chocolate granules; (Acetic acid)	285-89(d)	(60)	(a) Deep brownish yellow	C ₁₄ H ₆ Cl ₂ IN ₃	10.0	10.2

* Total of two isomers.

TABLE—Contd.

Sl. No.	Reactants ⁺	Appearance; (Solvent of crystallisation)	M.P. °C	Yield (%)	(a) Colour with conc. H ₂ SO ₄ ; (b) Shade on wool	Mol. formula	Analysis N%	
							Found	Reqd.
45.	5-Nitro-I+ 4,5-dichloro-P	Orange flakes; (Pyridine+ Nitrobenzene)	384(d)	(90)	(a) Deep golden yellow (b) Bright intense yellow	C ₁₄ H ₆ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂	17.1	16.8
46.	5,7-Dibromo-I+ 4,5-dichloro-P	Orange woolly needles; (Pyridine)	322-24	(87)	(a) Deep yellowish brown (b) Brownish orange	C ₁₄ H ₅ Br ₂ Cl ₂ N ₃	9.0	9.4
47.	5-Bromo-7-nitro- I+4,5-dichloro-P	Orange granules; (Pyridine)	325-28	(95)	(a) Deep orange (b) Brown	C ₁₄ H ₅ BrCl ₂ N ₄ O ₂	13.0	13.6
48.	5,7-Dinitro-I+ 4,5-dichloro-P	Yellow granules; (Nitrobenzene)	337-38	(79)	(a) Deep reddish orange	C ₁₄ H ₅ Cl ₂ N ₅ O ₄	18.1	18.5
<i>Section VII</i>								
49.	I+4,5-dibromo-P	Brown granules; (Acetic acid+ Ethyl alcohol)	305-306	(45)	(a) Deep reddish brown (b) Yellow	C ₁₄ H ₇ Br ₂ N ₃	10.9	11.1
50.	5-Chloro-I+ 4,5-dibromo-P	Dark red granules; (Acetic acid)	295	(42)	(a) Deep yellowish brown (b) Orange	C ₁₄ H ₆ Br ₂ ClN ₃	10.0	10.2
51.	5-Bromo-I+ 4,5-dibromo-P	Deep orange flakes; (Nitrobenzene)	305-306	(82)	(a) Deep yellow (b) Yellowish orange	C ₁₄ H ₆ Br ₃ N ₃	9.0	9.2
52.	5-Iodo-I+ 4,5-dibromo-P	Deep orange flakes; (Nitrobenzene)	322-23	(60)	(a) Brown (b) Yellowish orange	C ₁₄ H ₆ Br ₂ IN ₃	8.0	8.4
53.	5-Nitro-I+ 4,5-dibromo-P	Orange yellow flakes; (Nitrobenzene)	376-78	(93)	(a) Orange (b) Light orange	C ₁₄ H ₆ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₂	13.0	13.3
54.	5,7-Dibromo-I+ 4,5-dibromo-P	Dull red flakes; (Nitrobenzene)	328	(93)	(a) Golden yellow (b) Dull light red	C ₁₄ H ₅ Br ₄ N ₃	7.2	7.9
55.	5-Bromo-7-nitro- I+4,5-dibromo-P	Scarlet red woolly needles; (Pyridine)	358(d)	(90)	(a) Orange (b) Brown	C ₁₄ H ₅ Br ₃ N ₄ O ₂	11.4	11.2
56.	5,7-Dinitro-I+ 4,5-dibromo-P	Deep yellow shining flakes; (Nitrobenzene)	350-51(d)	(86)	(a) Reddish orange	C ₁₄ H ₅ BrN ₅ O ₄	14.9	15.0

could be isolated in the pure state, except one (*vide* Table, sl. no. 31) in which both the isomers were obtained in equal amounts.

The microanalytical data and other details have been recorded in the table. Thirtyfive of the indophenazines, which had bright colour, have been uniformly developed on wool, although the shades were somewhat lighter than the parent compounds.

Experimental

The following general procedure was adopted :

To a clear solution of the isatin in a minimum volume of hot acetic acid was added an equimolecular proportion of the *o*-phenylenediamine. The products separated immediately in most cases but to ensure complete reaction, the mixture was kept boiling for 5 min more. In a few cases, concentration of the solution to a small volume was necessary. The crystals were filtered, washed and recrystallised several times to give the pure products.

Dyeing was carried out from an acid bath following the usual procedure.

References

1. N. P. BUU-HOI, R. ROYER, B. ECKART and P. JACQUIGNON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4867.
2. V. Q. YEN, N. P. BUU-HOI and N. D. XUONG, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 1858.
3. N. P. BUU-HOI and P. JACQUIGNON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3095.
4. N. P. BUU-HOI, G. SAINT-RUF, P. JACQUIGNON and M. MARTY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2274.
5. N. P. BUU-HOI and G. SAINT-RUF, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1960, 1920; *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, **57**, 882.
6. J. S. FRIEDMAN, *U.S. Patent* 2627, 461 (1953); *Chem. Abs.*, 9153, **47**, 842.
7. K. N. SAREEN, R. P. KOHLI, M. K. P. AMMA and M. L. GUZRAL, *Indian J. Physiol. Pharmacol.*, 1962, **6**, 87.
8. E. SCHUNCK and L. MARCHLEWSKI, *Ber.*, 1896, **29**, 194.
9. S. K. GUHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **13**, 571.
10. H. D. TIWARI and S. D. DUTT, *Proc. National Acad. Sci.*, (Allahabad) 1937, **71**, 58.
11. D. PRASAD, S. SEN and P. C. DUTTA, *Ber.*, 1937, **70** (II), 2363.
12. S. K. GUHA, K. D. BANERJI and K. K. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 1011.